

A Core Design Study of Molten Salt Fast Reactor with Moderated Blanket for Transmutation of Long-Lived Fission Products

Ryan Willat¹, Puran Deng^{1,3}, Won Sik Yang^{1*}, Taek Kim²

¹University of Michigan, Department of Nuclear Engineering and Radiological Sciences, 2355 Bonisteel Blvd, Ann Arbor, MI, USA

²Argonne National Laboratory, Nuclear Science and Engineering Division, 9700 Cass Ave., Lemont, IL, USA

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803261

ABSTRACT

A 300 MWt fast-spectrum molten chloride salt reactor dedicated to the transmutation of long-lived fission product (LLFP) isotopes Tc-99, I-129, and Se-79 was studied. The reactor-transmuter is intended to complement non-neutron transmutation technologies as part of a DOE ARPA-E OPEN 2021 project concerning the development of a national transmutation facility in the United States. The design involves a central flowing-fuel core and an external D₂O moderated target-blanket where LLFPs are loaded as Tc-99 metal pins, Zircaloy-4 clad selenium pins, and MgI₂ salt dissolved in the heavy-water. To maximize the LLFP transmutation rates, a molten salt reactor with online refueling was chosen to minimize the parasitic neutron absorption in reactivity control materials during normal operation, and a tall core geometry design was developed to maximize the neutron leakage to the blanket. For reactor startup and shutdown, B₄C control blades were introduced between the fuel salt tank and the blanket tank. To eliminate local power peaking near the fuel tank caused by thermal neutron leakage from the blanket to the core, a thin annular Tc-99 target was installed next to the blanket tank as a thermal neutron filter. The calculated net transmutation rates are 31.55 kg/yr of Tc-99, 12.28 kg/yr of I-129, and 0.77 kg/yr of Se-79, all of which exceed their production rates in 3500 MWt PWR by a substantial margin. Other LLFPs produced in the fuel salt may be treated with the non-neutron transmutation technologies developed as part of the national transmutation facility concept.

Keywords: LLFP, Transmutation, MSR, Fast Reactor

1. INTRODUCTION

Fission reactor systems continue to face public scrutiny regarding the generation, handling, and disposal of used nuclear fuel (UNF) [1]. Methods proposed to address the long-term radiological hazard posed by UNF include dry-cask storage, vitrification, burial in a deep geological repository, and others [2]. Some of these, such as dry-cask storage, are interim solutions while a final deep-burial solution is refined. The effective capacity of deep burial is constrained primarily by the decay heat of intermediate-lived fission products such as cesium and strontium as well as the radiotoxicity of long-lived transuranic (TRU) nuclides and fission products [3].

Many studies have been performed worldwide for the transmutation of TRU in accelerator-driven systems and critical reactors, for example [4,5]. When the TRU nuclides are separated from the waste stream and recycled via extraction processes such as UREX, PUREX, or other advanced reprocessing techniques, the primary remaining contributors to the long-term radiological toxicity from UNF are LLFPs [6]. A study on non-neutron transmutation of LLFPs, led by Argonne National Laboratory, was started in 2022 as a DOE ARPA-E OPEN 2021 project [7], which aimed to develop a national transmutation facility concept for the transmutation of LLFPs without isotopic separations using energetic photons and protons.

It was found that for a wide variety of characteristic fission reactor waste streams, the following six LLFPs contribute more than 99.9% of the radiological dose after 10,000 years: Tc-99, I-129, Cs-135, Zr-93, Sn-126, and Se-79 [8]. It was also found that transmutation using photons or protons is physically viable for these LLFPs except for a few isotopes, but the energy required to transmute all LLFPs produced in a nuclear reactor exceeds the net energy output of the reactor, making the photon or proton

³Present Address: Hefei Institutes of Physical Science, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Hefei, Anhui, China.

* wonyang@umich.edu

transmutation option impractical [9]. Based on this finding, a hybrid approach based on a proton accelerator powered by a nuclear reactor was adopted. Zr-93, Sn-126, and Cs-135, which have small neutron reaction cross sections, are transmuted using energetic protons [10,11] while Tc-99, I-129, and Se-79 are transmuted in nuclear reactors.

Various preliminary performance analyses were performed for the reactor-based transmutation concepts, which considered various reactor types, including boiling water reactors (BWR), mixed heavy and light water reactors (MHLWR), molten-salt reactors (MSR), pebble-bed fluoride-cooled high-temperature reactors (PB-FHR), and sodium-cooled fast reactors (SFR). Based on the preliminary analysis results [12], we selected an MSR with online refueling that can minimize the parasitic neutron absorption required for the excess reactivity control.

The design objectives of this MSR were to transmute the above three LLFPs via neutron reactions without isotopic separation while generating sufficient electricity to drive a proton accelerator for use in proton-based transmutation. This paper presents the design approaches and LLFP transmutation performances of this MSR. Although we performed preliminary computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analyses to confirm that the selected design constraints are satisfied, the scope of this paper is limited to the neutronics performance.

2. TRANSMUTATION PERFORMANCE OBJECTIVE

The national transmutation facility concept is qualitatively illustrated in Figure 1. The LLFPs with high transmutation priorities are separated from the waste stream and divided into two groups. Nuclides categorized as Group A are transmuted most efficiently via irradiation with fission neutrons in a critical reactor, while Group B nuclides are difficult to transmute via irradiation with fission neutrons in a critical reactor because the production rates of Group B nuclides from fission reactions are larger than the transmutation rates. Thus, the Group B nuclides are more efficiently transmuted via spallation neutrons rather than fission neutrons. This work focuses on the neutron transmutation of Group A nuclides using an advanced reactor and LLFP target coupled system.

Figure 1: A qualitative illustration of the national transmutation facility concept.

When discussing transmutation technologies in the context of reactor-based systems, it is common to introduce the support ratio (SR) for target nuclides. As this reactor-based transmutation system is designed to transmute the LLFPs produced from other reactors in addition to the LLFPs it produces during its own operation, the SR is defined as the ratio of the net transmutation rate in the transmuter reactor to the LLFP production rate in a supported reactor:

$$\text{Support Ratio (SR)} = \frac{\text{Net Transmutation Rate in the Transmuter}}{\text{Production Rate in a Supported Reactor}} \quad (1)$$

For simplicity in this analysis, the annual LLFP production rate from the PWR, broken down by relevant isotopes in Table I, is used as the initial transmutation rate goal. The reactor-based transmutation system designed here must transmute, at a minimum, the LLFP generated in a 3500 MWt PWR to be considered viable for the national transmutation facility concept. Thus, the SR as defined here must be greater than one.

Table I: Annual production rate estimates from a 3500 MWt / 1175 MWe PWR.

LLFP	Production Rate in a PWR (kg/yr)
Tc-99	24.55
I-129	5.91
Cs-135	14.02
Sn-126	0.92
Zr-93	23.24
Se-79	0.19

In addition to the target transmutation rate, the reactor-based transmutation system must generate sufficient power to drive a proton accelerator in a proton-based transmutation system designed by collaborators [10]. Considering a 1000 MeV accelerator with a beam current of 30 mA, a power demand of 30 MWe is expected. This is approximately 10% of the power generated in the example PWR; to be feasible, a waste treatment plan should demand substantially less power than was generated in producing the waste initially. With these values in mind, for a conservative power conversion efficiency of ~30%, the thermal power of the reactor-based transmutation system is designed to be 300 MWt.

3. LLFP TARGET BLANKET DESIGN

The LLFP selected for neutron transmutation are Tc-99, I-129, and Se-79. The target form of each LLFP has a significant bearing on the effectiveness of transmutation. As the neutron absorption cross sections of these isotopes are larger in the thermal neutron energy range as opposed to the fast neutron energy range, it is desirable to load LLFP targets in a thermal neutron-spectrum environment. The loading of the LLFP with the fuel in a thermal MSR is limited by the physical size of the core and by the core reactivity constraints. This limits the maximum achievable transmutation rates and complicates the core design. By decoupling the LLFP targets and the core, both may be designed nearly independently, and the transmutation rates are only limited by the magnitude of the leaking neutron flux. For these reasons, the LLFPs are loaded in a moderated target region outside of the molten salt reactor core in this study.

To maximize the neutron leakage from the core to the target blanket, a fast spectrum core was selected, and the core height was maximized within the peak power density and fuel velocity limits. To minimize parasitic neutron absorption in the moderating media and maximize slowing down power, heavy water was selected to be the moderator in the target region. The LLFPs may be loaded as solutes in heavy water or as chemically inert solid targets, thereby preventing loss of target integrity.

Technetium metal does not interact chemically with heavy water at the projected operating temperature (< 373 K to prevent boiling) and may therefore be loaded as a solid pin. The optimal pin pitch and pin radius to maximize neutron transmutation of Tc-99 in a thermalized heavy water medium were studied previously by the authors [8]. An annular Tc-99 target was also introduced as a thermal neutron filter next to the heavy water blanket tank to reduce local power peaking in the core caused by thermal neutron leakage from the heavy water blanket to the molten salt fuel tank.

Elemental selenium, while not soluble in water, readily forms selenium dioxide when exposed to heat and oxygen. Given that the nature of transmutation generates heat locally via the (n, γ) reaction, it is probable that the formation of SeO_2 would occur if selenium were loaded as a bare pin like technetium. SeO_2 is soluble in water when exposed to heat and forms selenious acid, which is highly chemically toxic on ingestion. In the event of an accident scenario, human exposure to the acid could present a major safety hazard. For this reason, selenium was loaded in the form of solid pins clad in a material transparent to thermal neutrons. Zircaloy-4 was chosen for this purpose.

While elemental iodine is only slightly soluble in water, many of its common compounds are highly soluble. This, in addition to being very brittle in its elemental form, makes it a suitable candidate for a solute in the moderator. MgI_2 was selected as the material form for loading I-129 due to its high density and high solubility.

4. DESIGN CONSTRAINTS AND DESIGN LIMITS

As the nature of this reactor system is dissimilar from conventional power reactors, it is necessary to closely examine the constraints of the design. As an example, for optimal performance, power reactors

seek to minimize neutron leakage to maximize the neutron economy. In this design, however, high neutron leakage into the moderated target region is desirable to maximize LLFP transmutation rates.

To maximize neutron leakage while maintaining criticality, a fast-spectrum core is the natural option due to the neutron flux generally eclipsing that of a thermal-spectrum core of the same power by orders of magnitude. A TRU fuel recovered by preprocessing from a PWR UNF of 50 MWt/kgHM burnup was assumed for additional TRU transmutation, though it was not a major objective. A chloride-based salt form was selected for its preferable application to fast spectrum reactors [13]. Additionally, a large TRU fraction to minimize parasitic absorption in U-238 is preferred. The fuel composition of REBUS-3700 is a good match for these qualities [14]; the fuel used here is a modified adaptation of this composition. An average operating temperature of the fuel region of 925 K was selected to give sufficient safety margin to maintain the integrity of structural materials. Additionally, a conservative average power density of ~ 100 W/cm³ was chosen to limit the fuel flow rate for this study. This establishes the core volume to be ~ 3 m³. The core dimensions are therefore determined by the selection of the core height-to-diameter ratio, which was determined via a parametric optimization study to be close to two.

With respect to the neutronic analysis of the core design, the calculated steady-state k -effective should accommodate the reactivity loss of delayed neutron precursor nuclides decaying outside of the critical core region due to the flowing fuel salt [15]. To account for the reactivity loss due to the delayed neutron precursor drift, a target k_{eff} was conservatively set to 1.003.

5. MSR CORE DESIGN FEATURES

The resulting reactor design parameters were informed by a series of parametric studies that are omitted here for the sake of brevity. In summary, these studies included various pin loading configurations and orderings, the determination of an optical thickness of a technetium thermal neutron filter to enhance the transmutation of Tc-99 and reduce radial power peaking in the active core region, alteration of the active core height-to-diameter ratio to enhance neutron leakage into the blanket, and the enrichment of the chloride salt with Cl-37 to reduce the production of Cl-36 and enhance the overall neutron economy.

The final transmuted system based on a 300 MWt MSR core is illustrated in Figure 2; the rightmost image depicts detailed illustration of the target region to show the selenium and technetium pin distributions.

Figure 2: Illustrations of the 300-MWt MSR transmuted core, including moderated target pin regions. Color code: Fuel (orange), D₂O (blue), Tc-99 (red), selenium pins (green), steel walls (light grey), air gap (white), external graphite reflector (dark grey). Selenium pins are loaded closest to the core to improve transmutation efficiency. The B₄C control blades are withdrawn at normal operating condition.

Table II summarizes the core design parameters, and Table III summarizes the target design parameters. With the determined core dimensions, a Cl-37 enrichment fraction of 63% was used to yield a targeted k -effective of 1.003.

Table II: Finalized design parameters for the 300-MWt MSR transmuted core.

Thermal power (MW)	300
Fuel salt (mol%)	55NaCl-26UCl ₃ -19(TRU)Cl ₃
Core diameter / height (cm)	120 / 250
Heavy metal loading in the core (t)	5.31
Fissile loading in the core (t)	1.09
Insulation gap thickness (cm)	1.0
Container wall thickness (cm)	1.0
Blanket thickness (cm)	50.0
K-eff	1.003
Average power density (W/cm ³)	106
Fuel inlet temperature (K)	900
Fuel temperature rise (K)	50
Fuel salt velocity (m/s)	3.0

Table III: Detailed parameters of the target pin loading pattern.

Moderator composition	D ₂ O with dissolved MgI ₂ (100mg/L)	
Target pin length (cm)	250	
Target pin lattice pitch (cm)	3.37	
Tc Pins	LLFP composition	Metal Tc (100% Tc-99)
	Pin radius (cm)	0.25
	Number of pins	2442
Tc Filter	Composition	Metal Tc (100% Tc-99)
	Thickness (cm)	0.3
Se Pins	LLFP composition	Elemental Se based on EG23
	Pin radius (cm)	0.25
	Pin cladding	Zircaloy-4
	Cladding thickness (cm)	0.04
	Number of pins	366

The OpenMC Monte Carlo code [16] was used to analyze the MSR core design. The average power density of the core was 101 W/cm³, which is close to the target value of 100 W/cm³, with a power peaking factor of 1.5 at the core centerline and 1.3 at the fuel radial edge. Continuous online refueling of the active core region was assumed. Doppler and density thermal feedback coefficients of the fuel were estimated to ensure operational safety. This was done by altering the temperature of the fuel materials in either the cross sections or material density calculation, separately, to compare the effects of each. For the density reactivity feedback coefficient, the fuel density was decreased by 1%, corresponding to a temperature increase of approximately 38 K, while using the cross sections at the average fuel temperature. In the case of the Doppler reactivity coefficient, the cross section temperature was increased from 925 K to 1500 K while the fuel density was held constant. The resulting k-effective change and the corresponding reactivity coefficients are given in Table IV. For the designed fuel temperature increase from inlet to core average of 25 K, a power defect of 388 pcm is expected. Considering a 15% overpower event and accounting for a standard 300 pcm uncertainty in a criticality calculation, the reactivity control requirement of the system is 747 pcm.

The reactivity control system for the reactor was modeled as a set of twelve annular blade segments able to be inserted and withdrawn in the air gap between the fuel tank and the inner moderator wall. These blades are shown in green in the leftmost and center images of Figure 2. They are composed of SS316 clad B₄C with a 90% B-10 enrichment. The blades are 0.7 cm thick with a central absorber thickness of 0.56 cm. Their arc lengths are 30 cm and gap of 3.25 cm between them allows for sufficient space to account for expansion and vibration during motion. Details are tabulated in Table V.

Three cases are shown in Table VI to demonstrate the effect of the control blades on the overall system k-effective: all control blades fully extracted (operating conditions), all control blades fully inserted (shutdown), and single control blade failure (“one stuck rod” criterion). It is observed that the control system provides a sufficient shutdown margin.

Table IV: Thermal feedback evaluation of the 300-MWt MSR transmuter.

Case	Fuel Density (g/cm ³)	Fuel Temperature (K)	k-effective	Feedback Coefficient (pcm/K)
Base Case	3.46	925	1.00306 ± 10 pcm	Base
Density Feedback	3.41	925	0.99738 ± 10 pcm	-14.95 ± 0.02
Doppler Feedback	3.46	1500	1.00220 ± 10 pcm	-0.15 ± 0.02

Table V: Details of the control blade materials and geometry of the MSR design.

Number of Blades		12
Blade Arc Length (cm)		30
Gap Between Blades (cm)		3.25
Total blade Thickness (cm)		0.7
Neutron Absorber	Absorber Material	B ₄ C
	B-10 Enrichment	90%
	Absorber Thickness (cm)	0.56
	Absorber Density (g/cm ³)	2.52
Blade Cladding	Cladding Material	SS316
	Cladding Thickness (cm)	0.07

Table VI: Control blade reactivity worth calculation to verify capability of control blades to shut down the 300-MWt MSR transmuter.

Blade position	k-effective	Reactivity Worth (pcm)
Fully out	1.00306 ± 10 pcm	Ref.
All Blades Inserted	0.94451 ± 9 pcm	5855
N-1 Blades Inserted	0.94905 ± 10 pcm	5401

6. TRANSMUTATION PERFORMANCE OF TRANSMUTER SYSTEM

The transmutation performance of the transmuter system design is given in Table V, and an accounting of the neutron balance in the system is given in Table VI. Transmutation rate results are based on single-year target depletion calculations in OpenMC [16] simulations with sufficient continuous online refueling of and fission product removal from the active core region to maintain steady-state operation. Based on this one-year depletion calculation for the initial core configuration, the fractional transmutation rates of Tc-99, I-129, and Se-79 are 1.83%, 2.74%, and 10.14% in one year, respectively. Approximately 39% of the transmutation of Tc-99 occurs in the thermal neutron filter while the remainder occurs in the target pins, significantly increasing the transmutation rate. Target depletion will decrease the LLFP transmutation rates over time due to decreasing LLFP nuclide densities. This suggests that the pin targets, the thermal neutron filter, and the dissolved MgI₂ will all require replenishing after a sufficient fraction of the constituent LLFP nuclides of interest have been transmuted and transmutation rates are reduced below some specific threshold. Further analysis on target depletion, target reloading, and target shuffling, as well as more detailed fuel depletion/refueling calculations and explicit modeling of delayed neutron precursor drift in a flowing fuel system, are ongoing.

Notably, those LLFPs not loaded as targets have net production in the fuel salt. These net production rates are offset by the destruction rates in the proton accelerator spallation target system designed by collaborators [10] for all LLFP except for Cs-135, which requires isotopic separation for net destruction in either system.

Of the 42.72% of neutrons leaking out of the core, 35.28% are utilized for LLFP transmutation. Further design improvements such as adding an axial LLFP region or increasing the target region thickness

may improve this utilization fraction, but it is sufficient to achieve the design goals at this time. It should also be noted that the MSR model geometry neglects inlet and outlet fuel pipes for the sake of simplicity, which may affect the axial neutron leakage and absorption rates estimated by the OpenMC calculation. As the majority of neutron leakage from the active core is in the radial direction by design, this correction is expected to be small.

Table V: Transmutation rates of selected LLFP based on target depletion calculations in OpenMC simulations. Net production is observed for LLFP not loaded as targets, but the remaining are transmuted at rates greater than the production in a representative 3500 MWt PWR.

LLFP	Loading in Target (kg)	Reaction Rates in 300-MWt MSR (kg/yr)			Production Rates in 3500 MWt PWR	SR for 3500 MWt PWR
		Destruction in Target	Production in Fuel	Net Transmutation		
Tc-99	1720.75	34.34	2.79	31.55	24.75	1.29
I-129	447.61	13.1	0.82	12.28	5.97	2.08
Se-79	7.57	0.79	0.02	0.77	0.18	4.05
Cs-135	0	0	4.87	-4.87	14.13	-0.35
Sn-126	0	0	0.17	-0.17	0.93	-0.19
Zr-93	0	0	1.75	-1.75	23.4	-0.08

Table VI: Neutron balance data for the finalized core design based on reaction rate tally estimations.

Fuel	Absorption (%)				Leakage (%)			
	Target			Reflector & Walls	Out of Core		Out of System	
	LLFP	D ₂ O	Other		Radial	Axial	Radial	Axial
57.42 ± 0.009	35.28 ± 0.010	0.07 ± 0.0001	3.11 ± 0.012	6.40 ± 0.013	38.52 ± 0.048	4.20 ± 0.014	0.15 ± 0.001	0.75 ± 0.001

7. CONCLUSIONS

As part of a collaborative effort to preemptively address the buildup of LLFP in reactor waste streams, a design for a 300 MWt molten salt fast reactor capable of transmuting LLFP at a rate greater than their production rate in a 3500 MWt PWR while simultaneously providing power to a 30 MWe proton accelerator for additional waste treatment has been conceptualized. The reactor concept uses neutrons leaking radially from the cylindrical active fuel region into a heavy water-moderated target blanket containing technetium and selenium solid pins and dissolved MgI₂ salt. The resulting reactor design can transmute 31.55 kg/yr of Tc-99, 12.28 kg/yr of I-129, and 0.77 kg/yr of Se-79 with current design parameters. Those LLFP not transmuted in the target, namely Cs-135, Sn-126, and Zr-93, may be transmuted via the proton-based transmutation scheme designed by collaborators as part of the U.S. National Transmutation Facility concept powered by the MSR. Design safety metrics, including fuel thermal reactivity coefficients and a shutdown margin, were also investigated to demonstrate that the proposed control blades can supply sufficient negative reactivity to shut down the reactor in the event of an overpower event. Future work will involve the determination of an efficient target reloading and shuffling scheme to maintain high transmutation rates while accounting for target depletion under continuous operation as well as the explicit determination of the effective delayed neutron fraction β_{eff} and the reactivity reduction due to delayed neutron precursor drift.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the Advanced Research Projects Agency-Energy (Federal Award No. DE-AR0001578).

REFERENCES

- [1]. A. F. Holdsworth et al., "Spent Nuclear Fuel—Waste or Resource? The Potential of Strategic Materials Recovery during Recycle for Sustainability and Advanced Waste Management." *MDPI: Waste*, **1**, pp. 249-263 (2023). URL <https://www.mdpi.com/2813-0391/1/1/16>.
- [2]. P. Lappi et al., "From Cradle to Grave? On Optimal Nuclear Waste Disposal." *Energy Economics*, **103** 105556 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2021.105556>.
- [3]. R. Wigeland et al., "Separations and Transmutation Criteria to Improve Utilization of a Geologic Repository." *Nuclear technology* **154**, pp. 95-106 (2006). URL <https://doi.org/10.13182/NT06-3>.
- [4]. "A Roadmap for Developing Accelerator Transmutation of Waste (ATW) Technology," DOE/RW-0519 (1999).
- [5]. T. K. Kim, W. S. Yang, C. Grandy, and R. N. Hill, "Core Design Studies for a 1000 MWt Advanced Burner Reactor," *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **36**, 331-336 (2009). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2008.12.021>.
- [6]. W. Yang et al., "Long-Lived Fission Product Transmutation Studies." *Nuclear Science and Engineering* **146** pp. 291-318 (2004). URL <https://doi.org/10.13182/NSE04-A2411>.
- [7]. "Project Listings of ARPA-E OPEN 2021," (2021). URL <https://arpa-e.energy.gov/technologies/programs/open-2021>.
- [8]. R. Willat, P. Deng, and W. S. Yang, "A Feasibility Study of Photonuclear Transmutation of Long-Lived Fission Products Without Isotopic Separation." *Trans. Am. Nucl. Soc.*, **128**, 117-120 (2023).
- [9]. Puran Deng, Ryan Willat, and Won Sik Yang, "Feasibility of Photonuclear Transmutation of Long-Lived Fission Products Extracted from Used Nuclear Fuel," *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **199**:6, 907-929 (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.1080/00295639.2024.2403889>.
- [10]. G. Tikharyan et al., "Prediction of Spallation Induced Transmutation Rates for Long Lived Fission Products via Proton Accelerator," *digital preprint, arXiv:2510.05507*, (2025). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2510.05507>.
- [11]. A. Talamo et al., "Conceptual Design of a Thermal Accelerator Driven System for the Transmutation of Long-Lived Fission Products." *Trans. Am. Nucl. Soc.*, **132**, 262-265 (2025).
- [12]. R. Willat, P. Deng, and W. S. Yang, "A Neutronics Design Study of a Molten Salt Fast Reactor Core with Moderated Blanket for Long-Lived Fission Product Transmutation." *Trans. Am. Nucl. Soc.*, **132**, 1063-1066 (2025).
- [13]. M. A. Nasr et al. "Neutronic and Fuel Cycle Performance Analysis of Fluoride and Chloride Fuels in Molten Salt Fast Reactor (MSFR)." *Nuclear Engineering and Design* **413** 112506 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2023.112506>.
- [14]. A. Mourogov et al. "Potentialities of the Fast Spectrum Molten Salt Reactor Concept: REBUS-3700." *Energy Conversion and Management*, **47** pp. 2761-2771 (2006). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2006.02.013>.
- [15]. M. Aufiero et al., "Calculating the Effective Delayed Neutron Fraction in the Molten Salt Fast Reactor: Analytical, Deterministic and Monte Carlo Approaches." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **65** pp. 78-90 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2013.10.015>.
- [16]. P. K. Romano et al., "OpenMC: A State-of-the-Art Monte Carlo Code for Research and Development." *Annals of Nuclear Energy* **82** 90-97 (2015).